

VELOROUTER - TECHNOLOGY FOR URBAN TRANSPORT INTERMODAL SUSTAINABILITY

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Abstract

The European Commission Decision C (2015) 6776 established the specific European Transport Specific Programme implementing Horizon 2020, Part 11 "Smart, green and integrated transport", which promotes using clean transport methods, one of which is cycling. In order to ensure the successful functioning of an integrated urban transport system cycling has to be one of its components, which naturally fits into the overall intermodal transport system.

Due to limited funding it is important to understand which bike path network would be more efficient and ensure the greatest possible population transfer from other types of transport to bicycles.

The sustainability of an urban environment depends on quality of planning and correct crafting, which is significantly influenced by the technologies used to rule out acceptance of voluntary and intuitive decisions. One of recommendable solutions is simulation. The multi agent-based (MAS/ABM) bicycle path network and exploitation simulator (VeloRouter) has dual applicability as it is adapted to both the needs of municipalities and cyclists.

Introduction

Technologies are used to rule out acceptance of voluntary and intuitive decisions influencing the sustainability of an urban environment. One usable method is simulation when a computer imitates a process or phenomenon as if it was happening in real life. The basis of the urban environment multi-level model is a multi-agent Land-Use Category Change (LUCC) simulation model, which allows forecasting changes in urban zoning for a set period of time (Lemp, et. al, 2008; Ravulaparthi and Goulias, 2011). Each zone changes size is based on an empirical simulation algorithm. This determines the activities and the extent to which they can be performed in a specific zone, such as industrial or agricultural manufacturing, public recreation activities, individual or multi-storey buildings, hotels, green areas, etc., which in turn affects the placement of infrastructure, such as water and sanitation, electricity, and transport networks.

There are different LUCC implementation sets, the oldest of which are realised using cell automata simulation technologies, for example Metronamica (Linke, 2008; Kim and Batty, 2011; Riks, 2015), SLEUTH (Clarke et. al, 2007) and other LandUse Scanner (Koomen, et. al, 2011), WhatIf? (Klosterman, 2007), which determine several development limitations. The younger LUCC solutions, such as Fearlus (Macaulay Land Use, 2015), UrbanSim (Waddell, 2011), FUPOL LUCC (Deliverable 4.3, 2013) (see Figure 1) and others are usually designed using MAS/ABM technologies, which ensure tool compatibility and data exchange capabilities in a heterogeneous and distributed multi-level simulation model (Aizstrauts, et.al, 2014).

"Stambula LUCC 1" results

Figure 1. FUPOL Land-Use Category Changes simulator

In this case LUCC is the basement of the urban sustainability model, as it determines the functionality and limitations of any further models. The use of LUCC is the only way in the bottom-up simulation process. Otherwise designers can expect activity planning incompatibilities because there are no land, roads and inhabitants. Only by knowing the projected land area for each application, it is possible to create a reasonable design (see Figure 2).

Based on LUCC simulation results on the higher urban environment design levels it is possible to simulate changes in city demographics and potential tax income and expenses, as well as perform other urban policy crafting simulation activities. A sustainable urban transport system can be one goal of the model.

The European Commission Decision C 6776 established the specific European Transport Specific Programme implementing Horizon 2020, Part 11 "Smart, green and integrated transport" (EC, 2015), which promotes using clean transport methods, one of which is cycling. In order to ensure the successful functioning of an integrated urban transport system, cycling has to be one of its components, which naturally fits into the overall intermodal transport system. This means that bike paths, racks and the lease network must correspond to the transport system. Unfortunately, the lack of financial resources makes it impossible to construct bike paths wherever it would be desirable.

Figure 2. Multi-level policy crafting simulation model

Therefore, it is important to understand which bike path network would be more efficient and ensure the greatest possible population transfer from other types of transport to bicycles.

Cycling routes planning and design

The idea for VeloRouter originated in two EC FP7 projects FP7-ICT-2009-5 CHOReOS No. 257178 (2010-2013) “Large Scale Choreographies for the Future Internet” (Lescevic, et. al, 2013) and FP7-ICT-2011-7 FUPOL No. 287119 (2011-2015) “Future Policy Modelling” (Piera, et. al, 2013). This gave the opportunity to perform market research and understand the needs of potential users.

Cycling route database **Bikemap** (<http://www.bikemap.net>) is a huge collection of bike routes published by service users. Amongst others there are routes of weekend tours, longer holiday trips or the way to work. These routes can be joyful rides for tourists, single trails for mountain bikers or really long routes crossing whole continents, like the Eurovelo 7. Bikemap is free of charge. Bikemap works without registration. The elevation data has up to 30m (98 ft) deviance, therefore the distance markers and the elevation profile are not 100% accurate. Currently, there are 1,630,303 bike routes with a total length of 154,550,457 km. The user can mark his route on a map and publish it, as well as see its length and elevation profiles.

Similar functionality is offered by **veloroutes.org** (<http://veloroutes.org>), **routebuilder.org** (<http://www.routebuilder.org>) and **EuroVelo** (<http://www.eurovelo.com/en>). EuroVelo is a network of **14 long distance** cycle routes connecting and uniting the whole European continent. The routes can be used by **cycle tourists as well as by local people making daily journeys**. EuroVelo is currently comprised of 14 routes and it is envisioned that the network will be substantially complete by 2020. Similar products worth mentioning are **Pro-Plan**, **Topo-Plan** un **Bike Node Plan** (http://www.routeyou.com/route/routeplanner/overview_all/choose-the-route-planner-that-fits-your-needs), **MapMyRide** (<http://www.mapmyride.com>) and **CycleStreets** (<http://www.cyclestreets.net/about/>), which is a UK-wide cycle journey planner system that allows to plan bike routes from start to finish. It is designed by cyclists, for cyclists, and caters for the needs of both confident and less confident cyclists. A similar tool is **plotaroute.com** (<http://www.plotaroute.com>) that is a free worldwide online route planner for walking, running and cycling. It provides people with a simple way to accurately plan, measure and share routes used for leisure purposes. The website was launched by Spidersphere (UK) in January 2014 and is now used by thousands of people across the world every month.

The bike route planner **Flattest Route** (<http://www.flattestroute.com>) in addition to elevation profiles also shows route complexity, which is important for Sunday cyclists. **Velomap.org** (<https://www.velomap.org>) allows choosing not only the shortest but also the most user-friendly route. **RouteLoops** (<http://www.routeloops.com>) is the site that creates free, custom routes for running and biking that begin and end at the same location. There are several specialised route planners, for example for mountain biking **BikeRouteToaster.com** (<http://www.bikeroutetoaster.com>), which is a course creation application primarily aimed at Garmin Edge/Forerunner owners although other users without a GPS may also find it useful for planning rides. Another interesting tool is the bicycle route planner **Pro Velo Bern** (<http://www.veloroutenplaner.ch>) and the city of Bern which is based on OpenStreetMap data. The proposed routes are generated automatically based on this data. The quality and density of the OpenStreetMap data varies by region. The routing can be used all over Switzerland. The operators of the bicycle route planner strive to keep the bicycle-relevant data in the city and agglomeration Bern up to date. Nevertheless, it may happen that the suggested route can't be driven all the way or that cycling is banned on certain sections. Short passages through banned streets or footpaths may be proposed. Decisive is the signalization in the streets and the road traffic laws. The operators of the bicycle route planner assume no liability for the suggested routes. Regrettably, it does not include a simulation section, which would provide information about the possible load of the chosen route, as well as geofencing capabilities.

Skopje Bicycle Inter-Modality Simulator (EC FP7 FUPOL) (<http://www.fupol.eu/en/news/skopje-bicycle-inter-modality-simulator>) (see Figure 3) (Buil, et. al, 2015) is created to find a useable solution for bicycle station locations in the City of Skopje. To encourage intermodal transport, the citizens are also involved in the collection of ideas on how bicycle inter-modality can be fostered using a ticketing mechanism. The system helps the Administration of City of Skopje to improve the scheduling and resource planning, initiation and creating new projects involving the bicycle area in Skopje city. The above-mentioned simulator can be considered analogous to VeloRouter, however solution commenting and statistics aggregation capabilities here are limited. Simulation algorithms and results are focused on the needs of a specific large municipality and does not entail a detailed analysis of individual cyclists. Adaptation of the product is difficult and it is intended for use in large cities, which significantly limits the potential user base.

Based on the analysis above, it can be concluded that cycling route design and planning products mainly offer the capability of publishing cycling routes, but do not provide functionality necessary for municipalities to design a bicycle path network, which is critical for successful sustainability management.

Figure 3. Skopje intermodal bicycle simulator

The technologies are not designed to be deployed on the Future Internet (Software as a Service) (SaaS) environment, because the architecture of these tools does not conform to Service Oriented Architecture (SoA) requirements and is not based on web-service solutions.

VeloRouter - Dual use bicycle path network designing and exploitation simulator

The multi agent-based bicycle path network and exploitation simulator (VeloRouter) is designed in the Repast Symphony environment and uses OpenStreetMap spatial data. The product has dual applicability as it is adapted to both the needs of municipalities and cyclists. Each agent is a cyclist or a group of cyclists that move on a chosen route considering route load, traffic restrictions and the quality of the route.

VeloRouter provides municipalities with bicycle path discussion and geofencing opportunities by receiving feedback from cyclists directly and by using semantic search tools on social networks.

VeloRouter user authentication and authorisation is ensured using social networks: Facebook, Linked-in, Twitter, ResearchGate etc., given that cyclists are avid users of social technologies, whereas municipalities have the option to use individual registration options.

VeloRouter has two blocks: municipality and cyclist. The municipality is interested in some basic question: Is the offered cycling route map satisfactory? This is determined by summarizing potential comments during project deliberations. The second question is: Which potential cycling route sections should be built first? (see Figure 4).

The cyclists want to know what the load of a route will be in certain meteorological conditions on a specific date, as well as if the route is suitable for the group i.e. terrain etc. (see Figure 5)? Load MAS/ABM simulation provides monitoring of bicycle path network development scenarios and change management capabilities. Busy route sections are highlighted.

Figure 4. Routes map discussion view

Figure 5. VeloRouter route design view

The cyclist has the opportunity not only to send a message to the municipality, but also to publish his routes for public discussion.

During VeloRouter usage a PostgreSQL database is continually and automatically updated. With each usage this improves the quality of simulated load predictions. The database contains data entered by the municipality, which was gathered during interviews in public events, supermarkets etc., geofencing data, which was added by cyclists and other interested parties, as well as the planned routes of cyclists. Content is complemented by crowdsourcing semantic search data from social networks.

VeloRouter is an interdisciplinary science product that simultaneously uses knowledge management and semantic search methods, geofencing and crowdsourcing, advanced data visualization capabilities, as well as web-service and multi-agent-based simulation (MAS/ABM) approaches, providing further software deployment on the Future Internet environment.

Multi-agent based load simulation

It is preferable to pay attention to the MAS/ABM load simulation algorithm.

Initial data:

- Number of cyclists;
- Type of day (Working day, holiday, all days);
- Start time (HH: mm interval);
- Weather probability (summer: April – September, winter: October - March),
 - Summer day with precipitation (No, not likely, likely, yes),
 - Summer day without precipitation (No, not likely, likely, yes),
 - Winter day with precipitation (No, not likely, likely, yes),
 - Winter day without precipitation (No, not likely, likely, yes);
- Route (Start and end points);
- Weather conditions (Specific date and hour),
 - Temperature (C),
 - Snow (mm),
 - Rain (mm),
 - Atmospheric pressure (hPa),
 - Wind,
 - Speed (m/s),
 - Direction (meteorological degrees).

Output data:

- Route load per minute (data structure),
 - Route section (ID),
 - Day,
 - Minute,
 - Load;
- Route section load in total over days(total) (data structure),
 - Route section (ID),
 - Day,
 - Load.

Simulation algorithm:

The basis is Occupancy data, which is entered from the municipality and exploitation views ("Load data" from the input data list). Occupancy data contains the number of cyclists, which is considered the smallest entity. The entity represents a specific cyclist who uses the roads. For each such cyclist an agent has to be created, which, based on other attributes and input data, will participate in traffic at a specific time and day. Figure 6 shows the general calculation algorithm from the Occupancy data point of view.

Figure 6. Load simulation general model

The general load algorithm (see Figure 6) shows that data containing all Occupancy entries is read from a database and they are all consecutively processed (subprocess "Load calculation"). When all Occupancy data entries are processed, load data is saved to the database. Figure 7 contains a more detailed look on the "Load calculation" subprocess. To estimate the load of each route, initially the attributes of each cyclist are calculated (subprocess "Cyclist parameters calculation") based on model input data.

Figure 7. "Load calculation" subprocess expansion

When cyclist attributes are calculated, it is determined whether he will participate in traffic. The following conditions are checked:

- Is it an appropriate season to be cycling?
- Is it an appropriate day (working day / holiday) for the specific cyclist to be cycling?
- Is the weather appropriate for the specific cyclist to be cycling?
- Is road load adequate for the specific cyclist to be cycling?

If all these conditions are met, the cyclist participates in traffic and occupies route sections during a particular time (specific hour and minute) based on the calculated attributes. Figure 8 shows the "Cyclist parameters calculation" subprocess in more detail.

Figure 8. "Cyclist parameters calculation" subprocess content

The following attributes are calculated for each cyclist:

- Route for the particular cyclist (the route calculation algorithm takes into account road restrictions);
- Cycling start time;
- Desire to cycle on a specific date (summer/winter, type of day);
- Desire to cycle in specific weather conditions (data import from the Weather Forecast service based on date and time of day);
- Desire to cycle taking into account route load;
- Average speed.

The cycling route is calculated for each Occupancy entry during each load simulation session. If one Occupancy entry consists of multiple cyclists, all take one route, but the time can vary. The route is recalculated each time to be up-to-date based on the version of each route calculation algorithm, as for example road restrictions can change on a daily basis.

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Weather data is retrieved from the WeatherForecast service, which sends forecast information for the day by the hour, therefore if cycling takes longer than an hour it is possible to simulate whether the trip has to be interrupted. The MAS/ABM model verification does not rise problems, however validation depends on the capacity of data base therefore it can be done later stages of the project.

Conclusions

Simulation enables users to evaluate and predict possible outcomes to avoid voluntary decisions.

VeloRouter is one of the first simulators that takes into account municipality tasks, performs a social function and is cyclist-friendly.

One of the most important preconditions for a precise forecast is qualitative and credible data selection, which is usually realised using interviews and surveys, however survey confidence especially in sensitive segments is low.

Higher impartiality can be ensured using semantic search and data analysis possibilities in social networks.

Informative feedback is a precondition for every successful governance authority. VeloRouter enables this by offering commenting and opinion aggregation capabilities.

Basically all cycling route designers offer route planning capabilities, however there are very few that propose route load predictions for a route on a specific date taking into account meteorological conditions.

Agent-based simulation supports relatively precise load prediction so unpleasant incidents during a trip can be limited.

VeloRouter enables continuous prediction update capabilities, which are determined by the amount and quality of data in the database.

The software is based on open-source principles, therefore not only promoting dissemination of VeloRouter, but also ensuring clean code and user security.

The main tasks for further development are the use of semantic analytics and displaying results in a manner that corresponds to the user's perception, as well as their virtualisation and VeloRouter integration into a unified municipality information system.

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